

Projecting subnational fertility for Great Britain using Bayesian generalised additive models

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Abstract

Subnational fertility projections (SNFPs) are an important driver of subnational population projections (SNPPs), which then are vital for national and local governments and businesses to distribute funding and anticipate future demand for resources, products or services. In the United Kingdom (UK), official SNPPs are published separately by the constituent countries, each with differing assumptions and variants. We develop a Bayesian SNFP model for the three UK countries constituting Great Britain – England, Scotland and Wales – that borrows strength across the local authority districts (LADs) for the three countries and appropriately quantifies uncertainty. We cluster local schedules of age-specific fertility rates (ASFRs) to identify LADs with similar fertility patterns across age and year. We then apply a cluster-specific Bayesian generalised additive model which includes a global age-year interaction modified by LAD-specific random intercepts and smooth age and year effects. In terms of predictive accuracy of the rate forecasts, our proposed model outperforms a simple extrapolation method and naive freezing of the local ASFRs, which are important baselines in the literature. We also compare our SNFPs with official projections from 2008 and 2014, finding that our projections are competitive, especially at longer forecast horizons. Our proposed methodology has the potential to improve projection reliability and therefore aid local and national government planners in their decision-making.

1 Introduction

1.1 The need for subnational forecasts

A great number of decisions depend upon subnational population forecasts. At the national level, plans for distribution of central government resources to local government and health bodies will depend on current and projected population sizes (Office for National Statistics, 2025c). Investments in housing, rail links, roads and other infrastructure depend on future demand calculations, of which population forecasts play a crucial role. At a local level, educational bodies will similarly require information about future pupil numbers at a subnational scale to inform decisions about school openings and closings (Office for National Statistics, 2025c). In the private sector, businesses may take into account future population growth when considering branch locations and future investment.

Despite this undoubted importance of the local population in a wide range of contexts, methods for subnational population projection have been somewhat neglected. A recent review by Wilson et al. (2022) concluded that more attention is needed on this critical problem in applied demography.

1.2 Existing approaches to subnational fertility projection

To produce population projections at the subnational level, models must be developed for each of the three components of demographic change: mortality, fertility, and migration. Forecasting fertility at the subnational level is the focus of this paper, although some of the techniques developed here may be more widely applicable.

Existing approaches for the modelling of subnational fertility are varied. In their text on local population projections, Smith et al. (2001) split approaches according to whether they take a period or cohort perspective. Within the period paradigm, they identify the following approaches:

- *Constant rate* approaches involve simply taking the most recent observation (or possibly an average of the n most recent years) as the prediction for all future years.
- *Trend extrapolation* encompasses a range of techniques that aim to allow for trends in rates or summary measures to persist. This family includes time series models fitted to rates or summary measures (e.g. de Beer, 1989).
- *Synthetic projection* models relate the population to be projected to a *model* population via the calculation of ratios. These ratios are then applied to model population forecasts of future years to obtain the desired forecasts.
- *Targeting* methods are similar to the synthetic approaches described above, except it is assumed that ratios tend to one by some future date, so that fertility rates converge to the target population.

- *Structural models* attempt to predict fertility in terms of socio-economic causal factors.
- *Judgement* methods rely on expert or practitioner judgement as to future evolution of fertility trends.

Smith et al. (2001) also identify cohort-based approaches based on expectations of completed family size; and models based on theory developed by Easterlin that relates waves in fertility to the size of parents' birth cohort (Easterlin, 1966, 1976; Pampel and Peters, 1995). However, none of the methods mentioned by Smith et al. (2001) provide a formal way of borrowing strength across cohorts, or of quantifying uncertainty in predictions.

For the UK, official subnational population projections used by government departments are produced by the Office for National Statistics (ONS) via a 'synthetic population' type method (Office for National Statistics, 2025c). These projections are designed to be consistent with the fertility component of the National Population Projections (Office for National Statistics, 2025b). To construct forecasts for local authorities, the ONS methodology (Office for National Statistics, 2025a) calculates the average age-specific fertility rates (ASFRs) for each local authority for the five years preceding the start of the forecast. Adjustment ratios are then calculated by dividing each local ASFR by its national equivalent. For every future year, local rate forecasts are calculated by multiplying national rate forecasts by these adjustment ratios. Additional adjustments are carried out to ensure aggregated local births are consistent with the total predicted by the national model.

Although this approach has the advantage of ensuring local projections are consistent with the national total, it does not allow for local trends to continue into the future, and neither does it allow uncertainty in local rates to be accounted for. Probabilistic approaches may allow for a more principled approach that is able to capture local variation and trends, borrow strength across age and area, and provide meaningful probability intervals for future forecasts.

Of course, methods for fertility forecasting at the national level may be applicable for the projection of fertility at the local level. Bohk-Ewald et al. (2018) carried out a comprehensive investigation of existing methods for forecasting cohort fertility in a recent assessment exercise, finding that the majority of methods performed less well than the naive method that simply 'froze' rates at their most recent values. Among the approaches that consistently performed better than this constant rate approach were those of Myrskylä et al. (2013) and Schmertmann et al. (2014). The first of these methods is a simple but powerful heuristic that allows current age-specific rate trends to continue for the next five years, after which rates are held constant.

The method of Schmertmann et al. (2014) is rather more complicated: a Bayesian model is used to complete cohort fertility schedules based on priors that penalise cohort schedules and patterns of evolution across time that are atypical with reference to a collection of historical empirical schedules, incorporating information across many countries and years. With respect to cohort schedules, the prior penalises distance from a set of three principal components describing historical cohort

ASFR schedules. Over the time axis, the prior penalises deviations from both the recent trend of fertility rates and the most recent value of fertility rates, so that the strengths of both the ‘freeze-rate’ approach and the ‘freeze slope’ approach of Myrskylä et al. (2013) are acknowledged in construction of likely future rates. Again, the extent of the penalties applied to rates is determined with reference to an array of historical data.

Subnational fertility projections have much in common with approaches that attempt to forecast across multiple national populations simultaneously. A prominent example of such a multi-population model is that developed by Alkema et al. (2011) and Ševčíková et al. (2016), which forms the basis of the fertility modelling in the UN World Population Prospects (United Nations Department of Social and Economic Affairs, 2024). This method incorporates insights from the theory of fertility transition, allowing the fertility decline trajectories of individual countries to be partly determined by other countries’ past experiences through a Bayesian hierarchical model that considers fertility decline to follow an autoregressive process with a double-logistic drift term. This model allows common patterns of decline that first accelerate and then decelerate to be shared across countries.

This multi-population approach can also be extended to subnational forecasting. In this vein, in the work of Caro-Barrera et al. (2022), the approach of Alkema et al. (2011) is applied to the problem of modelling Spanish fertility. However, a more detailed examination conducted by Ševčíková et al. (2018) notes that a subnational extension of this approach results in inappropriate patterns of correlation between subnational administrative units. Instead, they find that allowing a scaling factor on national rates to evolve according to an autoregressive process performs well in predicting future national forecasts.

More generally, the focus on fertility transitions may not be appropriate when modelling subnational units in post-transition societies, such as the UK, which completed its transition from high to low fertility in the late nineteenth or early twentieth century. Additionally, the subnational model introduced in Ševčíková et al. (2018) does not focus on age-specific fertility rates, and so cannot account for the evolution of age-specific fertility patterns at the subnational level.

Another family of models applied to predicting fertility at the national level adapts the widely-used Lee-Carter method for mortality forecasting (Lee and Carter, 1992) to predict fertility. This approach, set out in Lee (1993), centres the age-time matrix of fertility rates before decomposing it into multiplicative age and time components using Singular Value Decomposition, allowing time series methods to be applied to the latter component. This approach has been extended by Hyndman and Ullah (2007) within the functional data analysis paradigm, and also adapted within a Bayesian approach as the fertility forecasting component in national population projections (Wiśniowski et al., 2015).

Other relevant approaches to subnational demographic modelling in the Bayesian framework include Alexander and Alkema (2022), who describe a principled and innovative approach to estimating the size of the reproductive age population with sparse data. Their approach is based on a cohort component model, accounting for varying subnational mortality and migration, but as the focus of that paper is on

the adult population, fertility is not considered explicitly.

More recently, at the national level, Ellison and colleagues have proposed models based on the use of Bayesian Generalised Additive Models (GAMs) that enable estimates of smooth functions across a range of demographic axes (Ellison et al., 2022, 2023, 2024). The model developed below extends this approach to incorporate the estimation of subnational rates.

1.3 Aims and Structure

In this paper, we develop a Bayesian model for subnational projection of fertility for Great Britain. Our aim is to allow the model to borrow strength from local authorities across the three constituent countries, developing an integrated approach with consistent methodology, hence enhancing the robustness of estimates in areas with limited data. We assess whether projections have improved reliability by comparing with official subnational fertility projections (SNFPs) and best-performing existing methods for national projections.

The remainder of the paper proceeds as follows. In Section 2, we describe the data used in the model, and present some of the patterns in the raw data. Section 3 sets out the forecasting model and the fitting procedure. The results are provided in Section 4, including comparisons to other models for this purpose. Finally, the paper concludes in Section 5 with some points of discussion and areas for future work.

2 Data

We consider all local authority districts (LADs) within Great Britain¹, of which there are 363 in total according to the April 2021 boundaries. To fit our model, we require birth counts by age of mother, year, and LAD, and corresponding exposures. Exposure in demographic modelling is defined as the size of the population at risk of experiencing a demographic event; in this case, exposures are therefore the counts of women in each age group. We use annual birth count data by single year of age (of mother) and LAD for the period 1993–2021, sourcing this data from Office for National Statistics (2023b) and National Records of Scotland (2023) for England & Wales and Scotland respectively. We note that due to disclosure issues, the birth counts have been aggregated across the youngest and oldest ages, so we have ‘Under 20’ and ‘40 and over’ age categories². To supplement this coarse information at the extreme ages, we also incorporate more detailed birth count data by single year of age for Great Britain, across the same period, from the Human Fertility Database (HFD, 2024). We obtain the exposures from mid-year female population estimates available from the NOMIS database (Office for National Statistics, 2023c), using

¹It was not possible to include the Northern Ireland LADs, and therefore perform our analysis for the United Kingdom as a whole, because data on births in Northern Ireland by age of mother and LAD are only available from 2008 onwards.

²The Scottish data actually has ‘41 and over’ as the upper age category, but for consistency with England & Wales we combine this with age 40 to give a ‘40 and over’ category for all LADs.

ONS Admin-Based Population Estimates (Office for National Statistics, 2023a) for the years 2011–2021³.

For a given LAD, age and year, we calculate the ASFR by dividing the corresponding number of births by the exposure. To visualise the variability in the rates over time and between LADs, we plot the annual ASFR curves for selected LADs in Figure 1. We see that the ASFRs progress quite erratically across age, this being particularly evident for smaller LADs such as Tewkesbury, while the rates are noticeably smoother for larger LADs such as Tower Hamlets. Furthermore, the age patterns differ substantially across LADs, with LADs such as Doncaster, Neath Port Talbot, and Walsall displaying very ‘early’ schedules (curves peaking at younger ages), while LADs such as Southampton and Worcester exhibit more of an average schedule (curves peaking at central ages), and LADs such as Cheltenham and Stratford-on-Avon present ‘late’ schedules (curves peaking at older ages). Despite these contrasting patterns and the noisiness of the rates, in general the time trends are similar, namely a tendency for ASFRs to decrease at younger ages and increase at older ages, the schedules therefore transitioning to a later pattern. This effect is particularly extreme for Tower Hamlets, which displays a rapid decline in ASFRs below age 30 to move from a very early pattern in the 1990s and early 2000s, to a very late pattern in recent years. These general trends are also evident when we look at all LADs together (see Appendix B).

³These estimates were used because revised mid-year population estimates following the 2021 Census were unavailable; we have since compared the estimates from the two sources, finding them to be very similar.

Figure 1: Observed age-specific fertility rate (ASFR) curves plotted for randomly selected local authority districts, 1993–2021. Each coloured line corresponds to a different year; the ASFRs plotted at ages 19 and 40 correspond to the grouped age categories 15–19 and 40–49 respectively. Sources: see Section 2.

3 Methods

3.1 Clustering the Local Authority Districts

Figure 1 demonstrates that although there are regularities in the age-specific patterns of fertility across LADs in the UK, there are also differences. There is also considerable random fluctuation in age-specific rates across year and age. Hence, in constructing a forecasting model, we aim to borrow strength across local authorities so that the forecasts retain the regularities and smooth out the fluctuations.

More detailed examination of the data indicates that it may be possible to identify common age patterns in subsets of the local authorities, reflecting similarities in the compositional and socio-economic characteristics of such LAD sub-groups. A clustering approach may allow different models to be applied to different groupings of local authorities.

It would be preferable to fit the projection model to all of the Great Britain LADs at the same time, perhaps capturing similarities between local authorities using a number of latent classes that determine forecast behaviour. However, the associated computational complexity makes this infeasible. We therefore decide to cluster the LADs prior to model fitting based on their observed ASFRs across the fitting period, using ASFRs for five-year age groups so that the resultant rates are sufficiently stable. After constructing a matrix of these ASFRs, such that each row contains the ASFRs for a particular LAD, we apply the K -means clustering algorithm of Hartigan and Wong (1979) using the `kmeans` function within the `stats` package in R (R Core Team, 2024). For a given value of K this algorithm optimally assigns the LADs to K groups, where LADs within the same group have similar fertility patterns across age and time. We apply the algorithm to $K \in \{1, \dots, 40\}$, using the ‘elbow method’ to inform our choice of the preferred value of K . This is a heuristic approach which determines an appropriate value of K as that at which the within-cluster sum of squares curve ‘bends’.⁴

We demonstrate the results of this clustering process by applying it to the ASFRs observed between 1993 and 2014. We present the plots associated with the elbow method in Appendix C.1, choosing $K = 6$ as our preferred number of groups. In Figure 2a we present a map of the cluster assignments, while in Figure 2b we plot the cluster centroids; for a given cluster, this is the average of the ASFRs from all of the LADs within the cluster. For ease of interpretation, we arrange the clusters in order of increasing mean age of childbearing (MAC), so that Cluster 1 has the earliest MAC (27.4 years) and Cluster 6 the latest (31.2 years). This explains why the peaks of the curves shift from the left to the right as we look across Clusters 1–6 in Figure 2b. In terms of the level of fertility, this decreases across cluster apart from Cluster 5, which has a late pattern but a high level of fertility with an average total fertility rate (TFR) of 1.76 children per woman. Cluster 1 has the highest average TFR of 1.95, and Cluster 6 the lowest at 1.43.

⁴See Giordani et al. (2020) for more information on the K -means algorithm and the elbow method.

Figure 2: (a) Map of the 2014-based cluster assignments for the Great Britain local authority districts. (b) Centroids of the 2014-based clusters, plotted as age-specific fertility rate (ASFR) curves, where each coloured line corresponds to a different year from 1993–2014; in the panel titles, the numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster. Sources: see Section 2; Office for National Statistics Geography (2021).

Despite these differences in the summary fertility measures, the time trends are generally similar across the clusters, showing a steep increase for age groups 30–34 and older, and declines for younger ages which are particularly evident in Clusters 4 and 6. Regarding the prevalence of the clusters, Figure 2b shows that they vary quite considerably in size: Clusters 2 and 3 are the largest with 100 and 110 LADs respectively, while Cluster 6 is the smallest with 13 LADs. The geographic spread, exhibited in Figure 2a, also varies: Cluster 6 is confined to inner London and other LADs with high proportions of graduates (Brighton and Hove, Cambridge, the City of Edinburgh and Oxford), while Cluster 5 contains LADs mostly in South East England and Cluster 1 consists only of LADs in England & Wales; in contrast, the LADs within Clusters 2–4 are spread quite broadly across Great Britain.

3.2 Model specification

We fit a Bayesian General Additive Model (GAM) separately to each cluster of LADs identified above. For a given age $a \in \{15, \dots, 49\}$, year y and LAD ℓ , we let $b_{ay\ell}$ be the observed number of births and $N_{ay\ell}$ the exposure. We assume that $b_{ay\ell}$ follows a negative binomial distribution with expected number of births $\mu_{ay\ell}$ and dispersion parameter ϕ , i.e.:

$$b_{ay\ell} \sim \text{NegBinomial}(\mu_{ay\ell}, \phi).$$

Our model then sets the logarithm of $\mu_{ay\ell}$ equal to the logarithm of $N_{ay\ell}$ (an offset) added to a number of terms which in combination make up the log fertility rate:

$$\log(\mu_{ay\ell}) = \log(N_{ay\ell}) + f(a, y) + \beta_\ell + g_\ell(a) + h_\ell(y), \quad (1)$$

where

- $f(a, y)$: smooth age-year interaction, unconstrained;
- β_ℓ : a LAD-specific random intercept which is constrained to sum to zero across LADs;
- $g_\ell(a)$: a LAD-specific smooth function of age which is constrained to sum to zero across the central ages, i.e. ages 20–39, for each LAD;
- $h_\ell(y)$: a LAD-specific smooth function of year which is constrained to sum to zero across year for each LAD.

We estimate the smooth functions using a P-spline approach (Eilers and Marx, 1996), expressing them as the product of B-spline basis functions with knots at five-year intervals, and corresponding coefficients to which we apply first-order difference penalties to achieve suitable smoothness⁵. For further details on the construction of the smooth functions, see Wood (2017) and Ellison et al. (2023). We specify a scaled t_7 prior on the smoothing parameters for the age-year interaction, σ_A and σ_Y , which control smoothness in the age and year directions respectively: $\sigma_A/0.01 \sim t_7$

⁵Note that we do not penalise differences between the coefficients of basis functions constructed from the first and second, and penultimate and last, marginal age basis functions, as the differences are large.

and $\sigma_Y/0.01 \sim t_7$. We specify a half-normal $N^+(0, 10^2)$ prior on the smoothing parameters for the LAD-specific age and year effects, σ_{AL} and σ_{YL} , which we assume are shared across LAD. To construct the constrained random intercepts, we follow the approach taken in Hilton et al. (2019), specifying a $N^+(0, 1)$ half-normal prior on the corresponding standard deviation parameter, σ_{RI} .

For the combined age categories at the extremes ('Under 20' and '40 and over'; see Section 2), we cannot specify the negative binomial distributions for the observations directly as we can for the interior single years of age. Therefore, for each year and age group, we simply assume that this grouped total follows a negative binomial distribution, and derive expressions for the mean and dispersion parameter of this distribution that match the mean and variance implied by assuming that the underlying single-year-of-age birth counts are independent and follow the negative binomial distribution specified above.

For all ages, we incorporate the observed aggregate single-year-of-age birth counts for Great Britain, b_{ay} , provided in HFD (2024) (see Section 2) by first scaling them so that their total across the fitting period matches the observed cluster-specific total, denoting these scaled counts by b_{ay}^s . Next we construct the expected annual age-specific birth totals, μ_{ay} , i.e. by aggregating across all LADs. We then specify an additional negative binomial likelihood term with dispersion parameter ϕ_{agg} , i.e. $b_{ay}^s \sim \text{NegBinomial}(\mu_{ay}, \phi_{agg})$. We specify vague priors for ϕ and ϕ_{agg} .

We also construct the implied annual total fertility rates for Great Britain, by dividing each μ_{ay} by the corresponding exposure N_{ay} to obtain ASFRs which we can then aggregate for each year. It is then possible to apply a prior to the TFR series, to incorporate our belief that this measure should change reasonably slowly from year to year. We specify this prior as a first-order random walk, with the standard deviation calculated from observed consecutive TFR differences from HFD (2024) data for all available countries. This prior specification is in a similar spirit to the work of Ellison et al. (2024), who apply such a prior to cohort summary measures in their parity-specific fertility forecasting model.

3.3 Model fitting

To investigate the sensitivity of our model to different time periods, we produce two sets of forecasts: 2014-based, where our training data is the period 1993–2014 and our testing data is the period 2015–2021; and 2008-based, where the corresponding periods are 1993–2008 and 2009–2021 respectively. We focus on the 2014-based forecasts in the presentation of the results for convenience, but present all equivalent plots for the 2008-based forecasts in Appendix D. We choose the jump-off years of 2008 and 2014 specifically because they are also years for which official SNPPs have been produced, and therefore allow us to compare our projections with the official SNPPs. As it is necessary to provide the exposures for the testing period as well as the training period when fitting our model, to enable a fair comparison with the SNPPs we use the 2014- and 2008-based SNPPs to provide the exposure estimates for the corresponding forecast periods. We detail the sources of the official SNPP

data in Appendix A.

We fit the cluster-specific models using the `Stan` software via the `rstan` package within R (Stan Development Team, 2024), which allows efficient sampling from Bayesian model posterior distributions through its implementation of Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) methodology. We fit the models using a High Performance Computing System which allows us to run HMC chains for all clusters in parallel, each on a 2.1GHz processor. In this way the time it takes to run a single chain is similar to that on a personal machine, but the parallelisation means that we can obtain all cluster-specific model outputs in the time taken to run the longest single chain.

For each cluster we run four chains each with 1000 iterations. The first half of each chain is used as a warm-up period, and the resulting samples are discarded, leaving us with 2000 samples for each cluster-specific model. These are thinned by a factor of 2 to reduce the memory required to load the results object. The time taken per chain roughly increases with cluster size, the time for the 2014-based forecasts ranging from 2.9 hours for Cluster 6 (13 LADs) to 17.5 hours for Cluster 2 (100 LADs). We investigated various diagnostics, all of which indicate that the model converges well for each cluster and both sets of forecasts.

4 Results

4.1 Model components

To illustrate features of the proposed approach, in this section we present posterior estimates of selected terms from Equation 1 resulting from fitting the model with data from 1993-2014. A more systematic presentation of the results is provided in the supplemental material. We begin with the fitted (posterior median) smooth cluster-specific age-year interaction, $f(a, y)$, which is displayed on the rate scale (i.e. exponentiated) in Figure 3. We see that the patterns in the observed cluster-specific five-year ASFRs (Figure 2) are closely reflected by these estimates. Also, the forecasted rates (dashed lines) predict similar trends across cluster, namely steep decreases up to age 30, and stability or small increases at older ages.

We plot the posterior median and 95% prediction intervals of the LAD-specific sum-to-zero smooth age effects ($g_\ell(a)$ in Equation 1) in Figure 4. It is clear from the plot that Cluster 1 tends to have very smooth age effects for its LADs, while the curves for Cluster 6 are more complex and often reach quite large values.

Figure 3: Posterior medians of the exponentiated smooth cluster-specific age-year interaction term, 1993–2021. Each coloured line corresponds to a different year, with the dashed lines indicating the forecast period (after 2014); in the panel titles, the numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster.

Figure 4: Posterior median and associated 95% interval for the LAD-specific smooth functions of age ($g_\ell(a)$ in Equation 1) for each cluster; each coloured line and associated interval corresponds to a different LAD; outlier curves are labelled; in the panel titles, the numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster; LAD = local authority district.

In Figure 4, there are several LADs that stand out and are labelled. The most notable of these are Hackney, Tower Hamlets, Brent, Southwark, and Haringey. These five LADs in Central London have a U-shaped age effect, indicating that they have considerably higher ASFRs at younger and older ages, and slightly lower ASFRs at central ages, compared to the other LADs in their respective clusters. Newham (Cluster 1) is also an outlier, but its age effect increases with age, implying that the corresponding ASFRs are lower-than-average at younger ages and higher-than-average at older ages.

We plot the sum-to-zero smooth year effects (denoted by $h_\ell(y)$ in Equation 1) in Figure 5. Cluster 6 again exhibits the greatest variability, with Clusters 3 and 5 displaying the least and therefore having the smoothest effects.

Figure 5: Posterior median and associated 95% interval for the LAD-specific smooth functions of year ($h_l(y)$ in Equation 1) for each cluster; each coloured line and associated interval corresponds to a different LAD; outlier curves are labelled; the vertical lines indicate the last year of the fitting period (2014); in the panel titles, the numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster; LAD = local authority district.

In Figure 5, we can identify some of the same outlier LADs as for the age effects: their year effects exhibit very steep declines relative to the other LADs in their cluster, indicating that the level of fertility has reduced at a much faster rate for these LADs. The forecasts of these year effects suggest that the declines are expected to stabilise in the years 2015–2021.

We observe that the long-term stabilisation of the year effects is present across all LADs. This is largely driven by the random-walk prior on the TFR (Section 3.2), which makes the implicit assumption that in the absence of data, i.e. when we are far from the forecast year, the annual fluctuations will be very small. Another general observation, namely that for some clusters few or none of the age or year effects appear to be significantly different from zero, is discussed in Section 5.

4.2 Fitted and forecast ASFRs

In a similar way to Figure 3, we present plots of the posterior median ASFRs for four randomly selected LADs within each cluster (columns) in Figure 6 for the 2014-based forecasts. We observe that the flexibility of our model means that it is capable of capturing the great variability in fertility patterns that we see within the clusters. For example, in the Cluster 6 column, we see that the LAD-specific random intercept captures the higher level of fertility for Richmond upon Thames, while the LAD-specific age effect captures the early fertility peak in Lambeth, and the LAD-specific year effect captures the differing time trends for the City of London and Westminster compared to the other two LADs (this is particularly evident at around age 35). We can draw similar conclusions for the other clusters.

Figure 6: Posterior median of the age-specific fertility rate (ASFR) curves, 1993–2021, for randomly selected LADs from each cluster (columns). Each coloured line corresponds to a different year, with the dashed lines indicating the forecast period (after 2014); LAD = local authority district.

To visually assess the fit and forecast performance, in Figure 7 we present the 95% prediction intervals for the first row of LADs in Figure 6, one from each cluster. Each row refers to a different year, and the black points are the observed ASFRs. In terms of the fit, the aforementioned flexibility means that the model seems to perform well in representing systematic variation across age and time, and the observed points consequently appear as a random scatter across the intervals. The penultimate row (2014) is the last year of the fitting period, while the last row (2021) is the last year of the forecast period: we see that the fit clearly worsens between the two rows as expected, however the intervals appear to include the vast majority of points.

Figure 7: Posterior median of the age-specific fertility rates (ASFRs) and associated 95% prediction intervals for a randomly selected LAD from each cluster (columns) and selected years (rows); the 2021 row is a forecast; black points are observed ASFRs (see Section 2 for sources); LAD = local authority district.

We also highlight the ability of the model to capture appropriately the greater uncertainty associated with smaller LADs such as the City of London. Furthermore, we note the plausibility of the ASFR fit and uncertainty at the youngest and oldest ages, where the progression of the rates is informed only by the HFD data.

4.3 Fit and forecast performance

To assess the fit and forecast performance more systematically, we focus on the calibration of forecast errors. In particular, as one element of calibration, we examine the alignment of the nominal probability of the 95% predictive intervals with the frequency with which the actual observations fall into these intervals – the empirical *coverage* of the intervals. In well-calibrated forecasts, the coverage of the 95% intervals would be close to 0.95. We combine the cluster-specific average yearly coverages into a single plot for the forecasts that begin in 2008 and 2014 in order to better visualise the differences across clusters and jump-off years.

We present the coverage of the age-specific fertility rates in Figure 8, noting firstly that the average coverages are more variable for the 2008-based forecasts, even within the first few projection years. This could be due to the LADs having more diverse time trends in this period of considerable change in national fertility levels following the 2008 recession (Berrington et al., 2021). We observe that Cluster 1 in particular reaches a much lower coverage of just above 0.6 in 2012, while the other clusters do not reach values much lower than 0.75 across the entire period. The 2014-based forecasts exhibit greater consistency across clusters, with very similar U-shaped time trends that differ slightly in level.

Figure 8: Coverage of the 95% prediction intervals for the LAD-specific age-specific fertility rates plotted against year for each cluster, for the forecast periods of the 2008- and 2014-based forecasts; each coloured line corresponds to a different cluster; LAD = local authority district.

In general, the plots suggest that the projection coverage appears to improve in the years further from the jump-off year. For the 2014-based forecasts, the sharp increase in coverage for all clusters in 2021 suggests that there could be a link to the post-COVID pandemic recovery in fertility (Sobotka et al., 2024), in that possibly the contemporaneous projections were underestimating the rate of decline in fertility rates and therefore performed better when there was a temporary reversal in this downturn.

4.4 Model comparison

We compare the forecast performance of our proposed model with several alternative fertility forecasting methods from the literature that have been found to perform well at the national level when forecasting cohort fertility (Bohk-Ewald et al., 2018). We consider three comparator methods which we adapt to a subnational scenario:

- **Freeze rate:** for each age and LAD, this method forecasts the ASFR in all subsequent years to be equal to the observed ASFR in the current (jump-off) year.
- **Myrskylä LAD:** for each age and LAD, this method forecasts the ASFR in the first five years to be an extrapolation of the average slope of the last five observed ASFRs; after this point, the ASFR is fixed. This method is a subnational adaptation of that proposed in Myrskylä et al. (2013).
- **Myrskylä National:** the same as Myrskylä LAD, except that the slope is calculated from the last five national ASFRs rather than being LAD-specific.

As described in Section 3.3, we also compare our projections with the official subnational fertility projections (SNFPs); data sources are provided in Appendix A. We apply these comparator methods to compute corresponding 2014- and 2008-based forecasts for each forecast year, age and LAD. In Figure 9 we plot the mean absolute error (MAE), median absolute error (MdAE) and root-mean-square error (RMSE) for the LAD-specific ASFR forecasts against year for the two sets of forecasts (rows). We note that the SNFPs cannot be included in this figure because there is insufficiently detailed data available for all the constituent countries of Great Britain. We also note that for age-specific comparisons, we omit ages 15–19 and 40–49, due to observed births by single year of age being unavailable.

Figure 9: Mean absolute error, median absolute error and root-mean-square-error for the LAD-specific age-specific fertility rates plotted against year for our proposed model and the three comparator models, for the forecast periods of the 2008- and 2014-based forecasts; each coloured line corresponds to a different method (see Section 4.4 for definitions); LAD = local authority district.

In terms of the time trend, we see that in general the values of the measures increase with time, which is expected as forecast performance should worsen the further we are from the jump-off year. We do however see a near-universal improvement in the measures of predictive accuracy in 2021 (see Section 4.3). The Myrskylä LAD method has the poorest forecast performance across the board, which is expected as the LAD-specific trend is likely to be unstable and prone to unreliable forecasts. For the 2008-based forecasts the freeze rate method outperforms the Myrskylä National method especially in later years, while for the 2014-based forecasts the opposite is true. This contrasting ordering of these two methods could again relate to the differing time trends at jump-off. The increasing-to-stable trend in the years leading up to 2008 means that freezing the rates is preferable to extrapolating the more positive trend, as this latter approach will eventually lead to greater discrepancies from the observed declines in the post 2008 period. Conversely, it is preferable to extrapolate the declines in the years up to 2014 rather than freeze the rates, as we do indeed see further decreases in the rates in the forecast period. This highlights the dependence of the success of the Myrskylä National method on whether or not the recent national trend continues.

Our proposed method performs the best across all measures and in both sets of forecasts. We present the analogous plot for the age-specific births in Figure E.2. We first note that there appear to be smaller differences between the methods when we calculate the measures based on birth counts rather than rates. The general ordering appears to be maintained for the 2014-based forecasts, however for the 2008-based forecasts the freeze rate approach outperforms our proposed model for the central section of the forecast period, before worsening again in the longer-term. From these results, we can conclude that our proposed model is highly competitive with the models used for comparison when looking at these sets of forecasts.

To produce analogous plots that include the official SNFPs, it is necessary to exclude LADs outside of England (15% of the 363 LADs in Great Britain) due to data restrictions. In terms of births, we are only able to assess predictive performance across both sets of forecasts on the level of aggregate annual LAD birth projections, i.e. births aggregated across mother's age for each LAD-year combination. We present the results in Figure 10, noting first the large effect that aggregating the births has on both the time trends and the ordering of the methods. The two Myrskylä methods perform very similarly now, which could be due to the errors across age balancing each other out somewhat for the Myrskylä LAD method. The freeze rate method tends to perform worse than before, particularly in the first few forecast years. For the 2008-based forecasts, the proposed model performs comparably worse in the central years of the forecast period, but is still preferable in the long term, together with the freeze rate approach. The official SNFPs perform very well especially in the first half of the forecast period where they attain the lowest values of the three measures, before steeply increasing in the last few years to 2021, therefore being the third most preferable in the long term.

Figure 10: Mean absolute error, median absolute error and root-mean-square-error for the annual LAD-specific birth counts plotted against year for our proposed model and the three comparator models, for the forecast periods of the 2008- and 2014-based forecasts; each coloured line corresponds to a different method (see Section 4.4 for definitions); LAD = local authority district, SNFP = subnational fertility projection. Note that LADs outside of England are omitted.

The 2014-based forecasts exhibit more similar values across methods. The two Myrskylä methods are now the least preferable in all except the last few years. The proposed model is still the preferred method overall across the three measures. However, the official SNFPs attain similarly low values in the centre of the forecast period, with higher values in the short and long term. Therefore, we see here again the importance of testing forecast performance for different jump-off years, as the ordering of the comparator methods can change quite substantially.

Overall, the results presented in this section provide evidence that the proposed model is highly competitive in terms of rate projections, but perhaps less clearly advantageous for birth projections for the 2008-based forecasts in particular.

5 Discussion and conclusions

This paper presents a novel method for the estimation of subnational fertility rates using Bayesian Generalised Additive Models. Dividing the country into data-driven clusters with similar fertility profiles simplifies the forecasting problem, and the groups that emerge appear to correspond with substantive knowledge about fertility, as discussed in Section 3.1. The model is flexible, and is competitive with the best applicable forecast models with respect to its out-of-sample performance. It provides predictive intervals around forecasted quantities, which may aid decision-makers in understanding the uncertainty around future projections of, for instance, school place demand. These intervals appear reasonably well calibrated, in that only slightly less than the nominal proportion of observations fall within the 95% predictive intervals in the out-of-sample experiments for most LADs, as seen in Figure 8.

We acknowledge several weaknesses of the approach which may be the subject of future research. Firstly, for computational reasons it was challenging to fit all the local authorities in one model using the `Stan` software. As a result, it was not possible to borrow strength *across* clusters in this modelling exercise. Similarly, determining cluster allocation within the model could also be an advantage should the computational challenges be overcome. A model in which cluster membership is dynamic rather than static could also be investigated.

There is also evidence that it may be possible to simplify the model with only small degradations in forecast performance. The flatness of many of the local-authority-specific terms in Figures 4 and 5 indicate that these terms are perhaps not necessary for every cluster and local authority. Bayesian model selection techniques may help identify which terms are required. Future work would aim to test these suggested simplifications, and examine the possibility of estimating approximations to the posterior distribution. Methods based on variational or normal approximations may reduce some of the computational burden and allow such models to be fitted, but with some trade-offs in terms of accuracy of the estimated posterior distribution. It may be that the costs of this approximation outweigh the benefits from additional sharing of strength, however.

The forecasts presented here span the periods 2008-2021 and 2014-2021, so

that the longest forecast presented is for 13 years. The performance of this model over longer time intervals was not tested, but in practice, it may be necessary to forecast for longer periods. The recent ONS subnational population projections, for instance, run from 2022 to 2047 (Office for National Statistics, 2025b).

Another area for consideration and future work is ensuring consistency with national data and forecasts, a well-studied problem in the forecasting literature (e.g. Athanasopoulos et al., 2024). Here, we have incorporated a likelihood term such that observed national births follow a negative binomial distribution centred on aggregated expected births for each cluster, scaled by the proportion of births that cluster accounts for. This pragmatic choice ensures that many local errors in estimation do not become unrealistic when aggregated to the national level, but there may be more appropriate ways of tackling this problem if all clusters can be fitted jointly. Forecasts are similarly constrained by the addition of a time series prior on aggregated TFR that prevents fluctuations in cluster fertility that are out of line with those seen in historical data. Such an approach could also be adopted to penalise deviations from a pre-existing national forecast, although some post-processing may be necessary to ensure subnational level forecasts aggregate precisely.

6 Competing interests

No competing interest is declared.

7 Author contributions statement

All the authors contributed to the initial idea for the paper. J.E. obtained the data; developed the model; estimated the final model; created the tables and figures, and drafted the manuscript. J.H., E.D., J.B., P.W.F.S., and J.J.F. contributed to method design and development, and aided with drafting and revising the manuscript.

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Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available from various sources, with specific references provided in the paper. Code to replicate all results in this paper can be accessed at <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18442168>, together with all data needed to reproduce the results that can be freely redistributed.

References

- Alexander, M. and Alkema, L., (2022). A Bayesian Cohort Component Projection Model to Estimate Women of Reproductive Age at the Subnational Level in Data-Sparse Settings. *Demography*, 59(5):1713–1737. ISSN 0070-3370. doi: 10.1215/00703370-10216406. URL <https://doi.org/10.1215/00703370-10216406>.
- Alkema, L., Raftery, A. E., Gerland, P., Clark, S. J., Pelletier, F., Buettner, T., and Heilig, G. K., (2011). Probabilistic Projections of the Total Fertility Rate for All Countries. *Demography*, 48:815–839.
- Athanasopoulos, G., Hyndman, R. J., Kourentzes, N., and Panagiotelis, A., (2024). Forecast reconciliation: A review. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 40(2): 430–456. ISSN 0169-2070. doi: 10.1016/j.ijforecast.2023.10.010. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0169207023001097>.
- Berrington, A., Ellison, J., Kuang, B., Vasireddy, S., and Kulu, H., (2021). Scenario-based fertility projections incorporating impacts of COVID-19. *Population, Space and Place*, e2546.
- Bohk-Ewald, C., Li, P., and Myrskylä, M., (2018). Forecast accuracy hardly improves with method complexity when completing cohort fertility. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(37):9187–9192.
- Caro-Barrera, J. R., García, M. d. l. B. G.-M., and Pérez-Priego, M., (2022). Projecting Spanish fertility at regional level: A hierarchical Bayesian approach. *PLOS ONE*, 17(10):e0275492. ISSN 1932-6203. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0275492. URL <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0275492>. Publisher: Public Library of Science.
- de Beer, J., (1989). Projecting age-specific fertility rates by using time-series methods. *European Journal of Population*, 5:315–346.
- Easterlin, R. A., (1966). On the relation of economic factors to recent and projected fertility changes. *Demography*, 3(1):131–153. URL <http://link.springer.com/article/10.2307/2060068>.
- Easterlin, R. A., (1976). The conflict between aspirations and resources. *Population and development review*, 2(3):417–425. URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.2307/1971619>.

- Eilers, P. H. C. and Marx, B. D., (1996). Flexible Smoothing with B-splines and Penalties. *Statistical Science*, 11(2):89–121.
- Ellison, J., Berrington, A., Dodd, E., and Forster, J. J., (2022). Investigating the application of generalized additive models to discrete-time event history analysis for birth events. *Demographic Research*, 47:647–694.
- Ellison, J., Berrington, A., Dodd, E., and Forster, J. J., (2023). Combining individual- and population-level data to develop a Bayesian parity-specific fertility projection model. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series C*, qlad095.
- Ellison, J., Bijak, J., and Dodd, E., (2024). Can incorporating parity information improve the reliability of fertility projections? Insights from a Bayesian generalized additive model approach. *Zenodo*. Version 1.0. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10535104>.
- Giordani, P., Ferraro, M. B., and Martella, F., (2020). *An Introduction to Clustering with R*. Springer.
- Hartigan, J. A. and Wong, M. A., (1979). Algorithm AS 136: A K-means clustering algorithm. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series C: Applied Statistics*, 28(1):100–108.
- HFD, (2024). Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research (Germany) and Vienna Institute of Demography (Austria). <http://www.humanfertility.org>. Data downloaded 11 March 2024.
- Hilton, J., Dodd, E., Forster, J. J., and Smith, P. W. F., (2019). Projecting UK mortality by using Bayesian generalized additive models. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series C*, 68:29–49.
- Hyndman, R. J. and Ullah, M. S., (2007). Robust forecasting of mortality and fertility rates: A functional data approach. *Computational Statistics and Data Analysis*, 51:4942–4956.
- Lee, R. D., (1993). Modeling and forecasting the time series of US fertility: Age distribution, range, and ultimate level. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 9(2):187–202. ISSN 0169-2070. doi: 10.1016/0169-2070(93)90004-7. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0169207093900047>.
- Lee, R. D. and Carter, L. R., (1992). Modeling and Forecasting U. S. Mortality. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 87(419):659–671. ISSN 0162-1459. doi: 10.2307/2290201. URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2290201>. Publisher: [American Statistical Association, Taylor & Francis, Ltd.].
- Myrskylä, M., Goldstein, J. R., and Cheng, Y. A., (2013). New cohort fertility forecasts for the developed world: Rises, falls, and reversals. *Population and Development Review*, 39(1):31–56.

National Records of Scotland, (2010). *2008-based principal population projections for council areas by sex and single year of age, by year, 2008-2033.* https://webarchive.nrscotland.gov.uk/20210314013900mp_/https://www.nrscotland.gov.uk/files/statistics/population-projections/2008-based-pop-proj-scottish-areas/08pop-proj-principal-councilareas-by-year.xls. Data downloaded 1 July 2024.

National Records of Scotland, (2016). *2014-based principal population projections for 2014-2039, by sex, council area and single year of age.* https://webarchive.nrscotland.gov.uk/20210314011255mp_/https://www.nrscotland.gov.uk/files/statistics/population-projections/snpp-2014/detailed/pop-proj-scot-areas-14-det-tab-ca-year.xlsx. Data downloaded 18 August 2023.

National Records of Scotland, (2023). *Table 3.14: Live births, stillbirths and maternities, by sex of child, marital status of parents and age of mother, Scotland and administrative areas, 2022.* <https://www.nrscotland.gov.uk/files/statistics/vital-events-ref-tables/2021/vital-events-21-ref-tabs-3.14.xlsx>. NRS provided the full time series of data on request.

Office for National Statistics, (2009). *Table A3-4, Principal projection - England population single year of age, 2008-based.* https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/ukgwa/20160115040554mp_/http://www.ons.gov.uk/ons/rel/npp/national-population-projections/2008-based-projections/principal-projection---population-by-age-last-birthday-by-single-year-of-age--england.xls. Data downloaded 1 July 2024.

Office for National Statistics, (2010a). *Table 2d, 2008-based subnational population projections by sex and five year age groups for Local Authorities in England.* https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/ukgwa/20150910145131mp_/http://www.ons.gov.uk/ons/rel/snpp/sub-national-population-projections/2008--based-projections/2d--all-las-and-higher-administrative-areas-within-england--2008-2033-population-projections.zip. Data downloaded 1 July 2024.

Office for National Statistics, (2010b). *Table 5, 2008-based subnational population projections with components of change (births, deaths and migration) for Regions and Local Authorities in England.* https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/ukgwa/20150910145131mp_/http://www.ons.gov.uk/ons/rel/snpp/sub-national-population-projections/2008--based-projections/5--all-las-and-higher-administrative-areas--natural-change-and-migration-summaries.zip. Data downloaded 1 July 2024.

- Office for National Statistics, (2016a). *Population projections – local authorities: SNPP Z1*. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationprojections/datasets/localauthoritiesinenglandz1>. 2014-based edition of this dataset. Data downloaded 18 August 2023.
- Office for National Statistics, (2016b). *Population projections – births by age of mother: SNPP Z3*. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationprojections/datasets/birthsbyageofmotherz3>. 2014-based edition of this dataset. Data downloaded 18 August 2023.
- Office for National Statistics, (2023a). *Admin-based population estimates for local authorities in England and Wales*. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/file?uri=/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationestimates/datasets/adminbasedpopulationestimatesforlocalauthoritiesinenglandandwales/2011to2022/apbefromdpmfeb23.xlsx>. Data downloaded 30 October 2023.
- Office for National Statistics, (2023b). *Live Births by age of mother and local authority, England and Wales, 1993 to 2021*. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/birthsdeathsandmarriages/livebirths/adhocs/1265livebirthsbyageofmotherandlocalauthorityenglandandwales1993to2021>. Data downloaded 9 October 2023.
- Office for National Statistics, (2023c). *Population estimates – local authority based by single year of age*. <https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/datasets/pestsyoala>. Data downloaded 22 November 2023.
- Office for National Statistics, (2025a). Methodology used to produce the 2022-based subnational population projections for England. URL <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationprojections/methodologies/methodologyusedtoproducethe2022basedsubnationalpopulationsprojectionsforengland#births>.
- Office for National Statistics, (2025b). National population projections: 2022-based. URL <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationprojections/bulletins/nationalpopulationprojections/2022based>.
- Office for National Statistics, (2025c). Subnational population projections for England: 2022-based. URL <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationprojections/bulletins/subnationalpopulationprojectionsforengland/2022based#data-sources-and-quality>.

- Office for National Statistics Geography, (2009). *Local Government Reorganisation (2009) Lookup*. <https://geoportal.statistics.gov.uk/documents/ons::local-government-reorganisation-2009-lookup/about>. Data downloaded 1 July 2024.
- Office for National Statistics Geography, (2018). *Local Authority Districts (December 2011) Boundaries GB BFE*. <https://geoportal.statistics.gov.uk/datasets/ons::local-authority-districts-december-2011-boundaries-gb-bfe/about>. Data downloaded 1 July 2024.
- Office for National Statistics Geography, (2021). *Local Authority Districts (December 2021) Boundaries UK BUC*. <https://geoportal.statistics.gov.uk/datasets/ons::local-authority-districts-december-2021-boundaries-uk-buc-2/about>. Data downloaded 14 August 2023.
- Office for National Statistics Geography, (2022). *Local Authority District (2011) to Local Authority District (2021) Lookup for EW*. <https://geoportal.statistics.gov.uk/datasets/ons::local-authority-district-2011-to-local-authority-district-2021-lookup-for-ew/about>. Data downloaded 18 August 2023.
- Pampel, F. C. and Peters, H. E., (1995). The Easterlin effect. *Annual review of sociology*, 21:163–94. ISSN 0360-0572. doi: 10.1146/annurev.so.21.080195.001115. URL <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12291060>.
- R Core Team. (2024). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Schmertmann, C., Zagheni, E., Goldstein, J. R., and Myrskylä, M., (2014). Bayesian Forecasting of Cohort Fertility. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 109(506):500–513.
- Ševčíková, H., Li, N., Kantorová, V., Gerland, P., and Raftery, A. E. (2016). Age-specific mortality and fertility rates for probabilistic population projections. In Schoen, R., editor, *Dynamic Demographic Analysis*, pages 285–310. Springer International Publishing, Cham, Switzerland.
- Ševčíková, H., Raftery, A. E., and Gerland, P., (2018). Probabilistic projection of subnational total fertility rates. *Demographic Research*, 38:1843–1884. ISSN 1435-9871. doi: 10.4054/DemRes.2018.38.60. URL <https://www.demographic-research.org/articles/volume/38/60>.
- Smith, S. K., Tayman, J., and Swanson, D. A., (2001). *State and Local Population Projections: Methodology and Analysis*. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, Netherlands. ISBN 978-0-306-47372-2. URL <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/soton-ebooks/detail.action?docID=3035561>.

- Sobotka, T., Zeman, K., Jasilioniene, A., Winkler-Dworak, M., Brzozowska, Z., Alustiza-Galarza, A., Németh, L., and Jdanov, D., (2024). Pandemic roller-coaster? Birth trends in higher-income countries during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Population and Development Review*, 50(S1):23–58.
- Stan Development Team, (2024). *RStan: The R interface to Stan*. R package version 2.32.5. <http://mc-stan.org/>.
- United Nations Department of Social and Economic Affairs, (2024). 2024 Revision of World Population Prospects. URL <https://population.un.org/wpp/>.
- Welsh Government, (2010). *Population projections by local authority and year*. <https://statswales.gov.wales/Catalogue/Population-and-Migration/Population/Projections/Local-Authority/2008-Based/PopulationProjections-by-LocalAuthority-Year>. Data downloaded 1 July 2024.
- Welsh Government, (2016). *Population projections by local authority and year*. <https://statswales.gov.wales/Catalogue/Population-and-Migration/Population/Projections/Local-Authority/2014-based/populationprojections-by-localauthority-year>. Data downloaded 18 August 2023.
- Wilson, T., Grossman, I., Alexander, M., Rees, P., and Temple, J., (2022). Methods for Small Area Population Forecasts: State-of-the-Art and Research Needs. *Population Research and Policy Review*, 41(3):865–898. ISSN 1573-7829. doi: 10.1007/s11113-021-09671-6. URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11113-021-09671-6>.
- Wiśniowski, A., Smith, P. W. F., Bijak, J., Raymer, J., and Forster, J. J., (2015). Bayesian Population Forecasting: Extending the Lee-Carter Method. *Demography*, 52:1035–1059.
- Wood, S. N., (2017). *Generalized Additive Models: An Introduction with R, Second Edition*. Chapman & Hall/CRC Press.

Appendices

A Official SNPP data sources

This section details the sources used for each forecasting exercise. Please refer to the bibliography for the URLs.

A.1 2014-based SNPPs

Projected exposures:

- England: Office for National Statistics (2016a)
- Wales: Welsh Government (2016). Note that we export the Female data for each individual reproductive age as a separate spreadsheet.
- Scotland: National Records of Scotland (2016)

Projected births:

- England: Office for National Statistics (2016b)

A.2 2008-based SNPPs

Projected exposures:

- England: Office for National Statistics (2010a). Note that these exposures are by five-year age groups, so we disaggregate them by applying the age-specific proportions implied by the 2008-based NPPs for England (Office for National Statistics, 2009).
- Wales: Welsh Government (2010). Note that we export the Female data for each individual reproductive age as a separate spreadsheet.
- Scotland: National Records of Scotland (2010)

Projected births:

- England: Office for National Statistics (2010b)

A.3 LAD lookup data sources

- To link 2011 and 2021 LAD codes: Office for National Statistics Geography (2022)
- To link 2011 LAD codes: Office for National Statistics Geography (2018)
- To incorporate 2009 structural changes: Office for National Statistics Geography (2009)

B Observed ASFRs

Figure B.1: Observed age-specific fertility rate (ASFR) curves plotted for all local authority districts (LADs) for selected years. Each coloured line corresponds to a different LAD; each black line is the average ASFR curve for the particular year; the ASFRs plotted at ages 19 and 40 correspond to the grouped age categories 15–19 and 40–49 respectively. Note that two LADs, the Isles of Scilly and the City of London, have been omitted due to small exposures. Sources: see Section 2.

Figure B.2: Observed age-specific fertility rate (ASFR) curves plotted for all local authority districts (LADs) for selected ages. Each coloured line corresponds to a different LAD; each black line is the average ASFR time series for the particular age; the age categories ‘19 and under’ and ‘40 and over’ correspond to ages 15–19 and 40–49 respectively. Note that two LADs, the Isles of Scilly and the City of London, have been omitted due to small exposures. Sources: see Section 2.

C 2014-based forecasts

C.1 Clustering the LADs

Figure C.1.1: Within-cluster sum of squares (*WCSS*) plotted against K for $K \in \{1, \dots, 40\}$; the *WCSS* values are normalised so that the first takes a value of 1.

Figure C.1.2: First and second differences between the within-cluster sum of squares values plotted against K for $K \in \{1, \dots, 40\}$; differences are plotted at the highest value of K involved in the difference, i.e. $2, 3, \dots, 40$ for first differences and $3, 4, \dots, 40$ for second differences. Differences for $K < 4$ are obscured by the intentional truncation of the y-axis to allow for better visual discrimination of differences for higher K .

C.2 Model components

Figure C.2.1: Posterior median and associated 95% interval for the LAD-specific random intercepts (β_ℓ in Equation 1) for each cluster; the LADs within each cluster are arranged in order of increasing posterior median; in the panel titles, the numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster; LAD = local authority district.

Figure C.2.2: Posterior median and 95% interval for selected variance parameters from the cluster-specific models. Referring to Section 3.2, the parameters are defined as follows: ϕ and ϕ_{agg} are dispersion parameters; σ_A , and σ_Y are smoothing parameters for the age-year interaction (in the age and year directions respectively); σ_{RI} is the standard deviation parameter for the LAD-specific random intercepts; σ_{AL} and σ_{YL} are smoothing parameters for the LAD-specific functions of age and year respectively. Numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster.

C.3 Fitted and forecast rates

Figure C.3.1: Posterior median age-specific fertility rates (ASFRs) and associated 95% prediction intervals for a randomly selected LAD from each cluster (columns) and selected ages (rows); the vertical lines indicate the last year of the fitting period (2014); black points are observed ASFRs (see Section 2 for sources).

C.4 Fit and forecast performance

Figure C.4.1: Coverage of the 95% prediction intervals for the age-specific fertility rates plotted against year for the fitting period, 1993–2014, for each cluster (panel) and local authority district (LAD); each coloured line corresponds to a different LAD; the black lines represent the average coverage; LADs with the most extreme coverage values are labelled. Numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster.

Figure C.4.2: Coverage of the 95% prediction intervals for the age-specific birth counts plotted against year for the fitting period, 1993–2014, for each cluster (panel) and local authority district (LAD); each coloured line corresponds to a different LAD; the black lines represent the average coverage; LADs with the most extreme coverage values are labelled. Numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster.

Figure C.4.3: Coverage of the 95% prediction intervals for the age-specific fertility rates plotted against year for the forecast period, 2015–2021, for each cluster (panel) and local authority district (LAD); each coloured line corresponds to a different LAD; the black lines represent the average coverage; LADs with the most extreme coverage values are labelled. Numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster.

Figure C.4.4: Coverage of the 95% prediction intervals for the age-specific birth counts plotted against year for the forecast period, 2015–2021, for each cluster (panel) and local authority district (LAD); each coloured line corresponds to a different LAD; the black lines represent the average coverage; LADs with the most extreme coverage values are labelled. Numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster.

D 2008-based forecasts

D.1 Clustering the LADs

Figure D.1.1: Within-cluster sum of squares ($WCSS$) plotted against K for $K \in \{1, \dots, 40\}$; the $WCSS$ values are normalised so that the first takes a value of 1.

Figure D.1.2: First and second differences between the within-cluster sum of squares values plotted against K for $K \in \{1, \dots, 40\}$; differences are plotted at the highest value of K involved in the difference, i.e. $2, 3, \dots, 40$ for first differences and $3, 4, \dots, 40$ for second differences. Differences for $K < 4$ are obscured by the intentional truncation of the y-axis to allow for better visual discrimination of differences for higher K .

Figure D.1.3: (a) Map of the 2008-based cluster assignments for the Great Britain local authority districts. (b) Centroids of the 2008-based clusters, plotted as age-specific fertility rate (ASFR) curves, where each coloured line corresponds to a different year from 1993–2008; in the panel titles, the numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster. Sources: see Section 2; Office for National Statistics Geography (2021).

D.2 Model components

Figure D.2.1: Posterior median cluster-specific fitted and forecast age-specific fertility rate (ASFR) curves, 1993–2021. Each coloured line corresponds to a different year, with the dashed lines indicating the forecast period (after 2008); in the panel titles, the numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster.

Figure D.2.2: Posterior median and associated 95% interval for the LAD-specific random intercepts (β_ℓ in Equation 1) for each cluster; the LADs within each cluster are arranged in order of increasing posterior median; in the panel titles, the numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster; LAD = local authority district.

Figure D.2.3: Posterior median and associated 95% interval for the LAD-specific smooth functions of age ($g_\ell(a)$ in Equation 1) for each cluster; each coloured line and associated interval corresponds to a different LAD; outlier curves are labelled; in the panel titles, the numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster; LAD = local authority district.

Figure D.2.4: Posterior median and associated 95% interval for the LAD-specific smooth functions of year ($h_\ell(y)$ in Equation 1) for each cluster; each coloured line and associated interval corresponds to a different LAD; outlier curves are labelled; the vertical lines indicate the last year of the fitting period (2008); in the panel titles, the numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster; LAD = local authority district.

Figure D.2.5: Posterior median and 95% interval for selected variance parameters from the cluster-specific models. Referring to Section 3.2, the parameters are defined as follows: ϕ and ϕ_{agg} are dispersion parameters; σ_A , and σ_Y are smoothing parameters for the age-year interaction (in the age and year directions respectively); σ_{RI} is the standard deviation parameter for the LAD-specific random intercepts; σ_{AL} and σ_{YL} are smoothing parameters for the LAD-specific functions of age and year respectively. Numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster.

D.3 Fitted and forecast ASFRs

Figure D.3.1: Posterior median age-specific fertility rate (ASFR) curves, 1993–2021, for randomly selected LADs from each cluster (columns). Each coloured line corresponds to a different year, with the dashed lines indicating the forecast period (after 2008).

Figure D.3.2: Posterior median age-specific fertility rates (ASFRs) and associated 95% prediction intervals for a randomly selected LAD from each cluster (columns) and selected years (rows); the 2014 and 2021 rows are forecasts; black points are observed ASFRs (see Section 2 for sources).

Figure D.3.3: Posterior median age-specific fertility rates (ASFRs) and associated 95% prediction intervals for a randomly selected LAD from each cluster (columns) and selected ages (rows); the vertical lines indicate the last year of the fitting period (2008); black points are observed ASFRs (see Section 2 for sources).

D.4 Fit and forecast performance

Figure D.4.1: Coverage of the 95% prediction intervals for the age-specific fertility rates plotted against year for the fitting period, 1993–2008, for each cluster (panel) and local authority district (LAD); each coloured line corresponds to a different LAD; the black lines represent the average coverage; LADs with the most extreme coverage values are labelled. Numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster.

Figure D.4.2: Coverage of the 95% prediction intervals for the age-specific birth counts plotted against year for the fitting period, 1993–2008, for each cluster (panel) and local authority district (LAD); each coloured line corresponds to a different LAD; the black lines represent the average coverage; LADs with the most extreme coverage values are labelled. Numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster.

Figure D.4.3: Coverage of the 95% prediction intervals for the age-specific fertility rates plotted against year for the forecast period, 2009–2021, for each cluster (panel) and local authority district (LAD); each coloured line corresponds to a different LAD; the black lines represent the average coverage; LADs with the most extreme coverage values are labelled. Numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster.

Figure D.4.4: Coverage of the 95% prediction intervals for the age-specific birth counts plotted against year for the forecast period, 2009–2021, for each cluster (panel) and local authority district (LAD); each coloured line corresponds to a different LAD; the black lines represent the average coverage; LADs with the most extreme coverage values are labelled. Numbers in parentheses indicate the size of the corresponding cluster.

E 2008- and 2014-based forecasts

Figure E.1: Coverage of the 95% prediction intervals for the LAD-specific age-specific birth counts plotted against year for each cluster, for the forecast periods of the 2008- and 2014-based forecasts; each coloured line corresponds to a different cluster; LAD = local authority district.

Figure E.2: Mean absolute error, median absolute error and root-mean-square-error for the LAD-specific age-specific birth counts plotted against year for our proposed model and the three comparator models, for the forecast periods of the 2008- and 2014-based forecasts; each coloured line corresponds to a different method (see Section 4.4 for definitions); LAD = local authority district.

Figure E.3: Mean absolute error, median absolute error and root-mean-square-error for the LAD-specific age-specific fertility rates plotted against year for our proposed model and the three comparator models, for the forecast periods of the 2008- and 2014-based forecasts; each coloured line corresponds to a different method (see Section 4.4 for definitions); LAD = local authority district, SNFP = subnational fertility projection. Note that LADs outside of England are omitted, and that the summary statistics for the SNFP model could only be calculated for the 2014-based forecasts.